

DSC /(μ V/mg)

Flow /(ml/min)

Main 2024-07-22 13:40 User: dsc_b

Instrument : NETZSCH DSC 214		File : C:\NETZSCH\Proteus80\DATA\2024\Juli\Sample Id 166137\RN1.ngb-sdg		
Project : Sample ID 166137	Sample : RN1, 7.20 mg	Range : 600°C/10.0(K/min)/25°C	Atmosphere : O2, 20.0ml/min / N2, 40.0ml/min	
Identity : RN1	Reference :	Sample car./TC : DSC 214 Corona sensor / E	Corr/m. range : 0:0:0/5000 μV	
Date/time : 22/07/2024 11:17:27	Material : Serbuk	Mode/type of meas. : DSC / Sample		
Laboratory : PUSAT RISET KIMIA	Corr./temp.cal : -- / TCALZERO.TMX	Segments : 2/2		
Operator : Hanif dan Fida	Sens.file : SENZERO.EXX	Crucible : Standard Al 25 μl , pierced lid		